

Digital Behaviour and Mental Health: Exploring Online Identity, Disinhibition, and Self-presentation among College Students

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With the growing usage of social media in day-to-day life, it has become necessary to investigate the manner in which young individuals present themselves on social media platforms. The current study investigates the relationship between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation among college-going youth aged 18-25 years. The participants for the study were chosen using convenience sampling, and the sample included 20 students (12 females, 6 males, & 2 others). A correlational research design was employed. The study used self-constructed scales designed by the researcher, namely the Mental Health Scale (2025), Online Disinhibition Scale (2025), and Online Identity and Self-Presentation Scale (2025). The questionnaire was conducted using Google Forms. Pearson's product-moment correlation was utilized to investigate the relationships between the variables. A strong positive correlation was found between mental health and online identity and self-presentation, indicating that students who present themselves more genuinely online tend to have better mental health. However, no significant correlation was found between mental health and online disinhibition, or between online disinhibition and online identity and self-presentation. The results should be considered in light of the small sample size and self-report nature of the data. Future studies could consider using larger and more varied samples, and mixed-method designs to further explore the relationship between digital patterns of behavior and mental health.

Keywords: Mental health, online identity, self-presentation, social media behavior, digital psychology

The rise in the use of social media has greatly affected the manner in which people communicate and construct their identities. Among college students aged 18-25 years, social media sites have become an essential part of their lives (Hjetland et al., 2024; Yang & Brown, 2015). This stage of development is characterized by exploration, identity formation, and emotional sensitivity, making young people more susceptible to peer validation and social comparison.

Digital behavior is the manner in which people interact, communicate, express themselves, and construct their identities in online environments. It encompasses behaviors such as online self-presentation, social networking site use, digital communication styles, and online disinhibition. These behaviors affect how people see themselves and how others see them in online environments.

Mental health is the emotional, psychological, and social well-being of an individual. It is what helps people think, feel, and manage their emotions, as well as deal with stress and interact with others. In recent years, there has been a growing concern about the mental health of young adults, particularly with regards to academic pressures, social comparisons, and participation in online communities (Biester et al., 2022; Hjetland et al., 2024). Online communities tend to promote the presentation of an idealized self,

which can affect self-esteem and psychological well-being.

The relationship between digital behavior and mental health is based on the mutual impact that both have on each other. People with good mental health may display more genuine and positive forms of self-presentation online, while excessive comparison, negative comments, or impulsive online expression can negatively influence emotional regulation and mental health. Online disinhibition, which refers to the tendency of people to be more open or impulsive in online environments (Suler, 2004) can either promote healthy self-expression or lead to psychological problems depending on the context. Excessive or negative online disinhibition can negatively influence emotional regulation and mental health (Syrjämäki et al., 2024).

The current study sought to investigate the relationship between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation among college students aged 18-25 years. Pearson's product moment correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between the variables. Although there were no significant relationships found between mental health and online disinhibition or between online disinhibition and online identity and self-presentation, there was a significant positive relationship found between mental health and online identity and self-presentation. Despite the limitations of the study, it is an important contribution to understanding the relationship between digital behavioral patterns and psychological well-being.

Review of Literature

Recent research on digital behavior has been focused on the relationship between mental health and online engagement, especially on how people display themselves, express emotions, and create identities online. With the growing effect of social media,

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researchers have been exploring key variables like mental health, online disinhibition, online identity, and self-presentation to understand the distinction between online and offline behavior.

Researchers Hjetland et al. (2024) explored the link between mental health and self-presentation among people aged 13 to 19 years and found that those who put more effort into their online presentation reported higher levels of anxiety and sadness. This shows that increased pressure for self-presentation can have a negative effect on mental health. In a similar study, Syrjämäki et al. (2024) explored online disinhibition among people aged 18-45 years and found that respondents who had issues with emotional expression offline were more likely to display disinhibited behavior online. This behavior was linked to both increased expressive liberty and negative mental processes.

However, recent studies have broadened the concept of online disinhibition by investigating its psychological processes in modern online settings. Syrjämäki et al. (2024) concluded that online disinhibition acts as a mediator between difficulties in emotional regulation and uncivil or impulsive online communication, emphasizing how the absence of social cues and the perception of anonymity can affect behavioral manifestations in online contexts. Similarly, Stuart and Scott (2021) noted that online settings reduce social inhibition, making it easier for people to communicate their thoughts and feelings compared to offline interactions. This lack of inhibition was discovered to affect self-presentation behaviors, allowing people to express themselves genuinely while also having the potential for negative emotional experiences. On the basis of this understanding, Stuart and Scott (2021) argued that online disinhibition leads to online identity exploration, as people with reduced inhibition are more likely to test various dimensions of identity expression.

Further evidence supporting the link between mental health and online identity was provided by Biester et al. (2022) who investigated the Reddit communities revolving around users talking about depression. The results showed that people suffering from psychological issues tend to use online platforms to display vulnerability and create online identities that feel safer and more authentic. Similarly, Yang and Brown (2015) concluded that authentic self-presentation among college students was linked to more developed identity and higher self-esteem.

It appears that mental health, online disinhibition, online identity, and self-presentation are highly interrelated concepts. Nevertheless, the desire for the idealized online self could be a source of psychological distress; online platforms are also a crucial environment for the expression of emotions, exploration of identity, and self-discovery.

Method

Participants

The study involved 20 college students aged between 18 and 25 years. The participants were selected using convenience sampling. The participants included 12 females, 6 males, and 2 participants who identified themselves as others. All the participants were currently enrolled in undergraduate programs.

Measures

The data was collected through a self-report questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire consisted of three self-designed

scales: the Mental Health Scale (2025), the Online Disinhibition Scale (2025), and the Online Identity and Self-Presentation Scale (2025). The items in the scales were measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = *Strongly Disagree* to 5 = *Strongly Agree*. The scales were intended to measure emotional well-being, online behavioral expression, and online self-presentation among college students.

Since the study had an exploratory design and was conducted on a small sample ($N=20$), the scales were developed for the purpose of this study. The reliability of the scales was tested using Cronbach's alpha. The Mental Health Scale had acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .75$), while the Online Identity and Self-Presentation Scale had moderate reliability ($\alpha = .67$). The Online Disinhibition Scale had improved internal consistency ($\alpha = .51$) after slight modification based on the reliability analysis. The questionnaire was distributed using Google Forms

Procedure

Before the commencement of data collection, the participants were required to give their consent. This was to ensure that the participants were voluntary and that their responses would remain confidential.

After the consent procedure, the participants were required to provide demographic information, such as age and gender.

Later, the three scales developed by the researcher, namely the Mental Health Scale (2025), the Online Disinhibition Scale (2025), and the Online Identity and Self-Presentation Scale (2025), were used. The participants were asked to respond to the questionnaire according to their personal experiences online.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis to determine the relationship between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation. The descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, and range were calculated to determine the nature of the data.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Mental Health, Online Disinhibition, and Online Identity and Self-Presentation

	Mental Health	Online Disinhibition	Online Identity and Self-Presentation
Mean	12.75	11.10	10.65
Standard Deviation	3.78	2.45	4.15
Variance	14.30	5.99	17.19
Skewness	-1.00	-0.15	-0.04
Kurtosis	0.27	-0.47	-1.37
Range	13	9	13

The descriptive statistics of the variables in Table 1 include mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation. The standard deviations of mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation were 3.78, 2.45, and 4.15 respectively. The variances of mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation were 14.30, 5.99 and 17.19 respectively. The skewness of mental health, online

disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation were -1.00, -0.15, and -1.37, respectively. The values of both skewness and kurtosis were within the acceptable limit of ± 2 , indicating homogeneity and normality of the data. The ranges of mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation were 13, 9, and 13, respectively.

Table 2

Pearson's Product-Moment Correlations among Mental Health, Online Disinhibition, and Online Identity and Self-Presentation

	Mental Health	Online disinhibition	Online Identity and Self-Presentation
Mental Health	-	0.16	0.45*
Online Disinhibition	-	-	0.22
Online Identity and Self-Presentation	-	-	-

Note. $N = 20$, $p < .05$ (two-tailed)

Pearson product moment correlation analysis was used to investigate the inter-relationships between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation. The results showed a positive significant relationship between mental health and online identity and self-presentation. However, the relationship between mental health and online disinhibition, as well as online disinhibition and online identity and self-presentation, was not significant. The non-significant results can be explained by the small sample size, the use of online self-reporting, and the presence of social desirability bias, which may have influenced the respondents to present themselves in a more positive way.

Discussion

The current study investigated the relationship between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation in college students aged 18-25 years. The results showed a significant positive relationship between mental health and online identity and self-presentation, indicating that people with better mental health may present themselves in more authentic and constructive ways online.

This result is consistent with the study of Yang and Brown (2015) who found that authentic online expression is linked to better identity development and increased self-esteem during the transition to college. Likewise, Biester et al. (2022) emphasized that online platforms can be a supportive context for emotional expression and identity development, which may be related to psychological well-being. These results suggest that online platforms are not necessarily detrimental but rather a significant context for identity exploration when individuals have relatively stable mental health.

Conversely, there were no significant associations found between mental health and online disinhibition or between online disinhibition and online identity and self-presentation. Although previous studies have indicated that online disinhibition may impact the expression of emotions and behavioral outcomes (Suler, 2004; Syrjämäki et al., 2024) the lack of significant associations in the current study may suggest that online disinhibition is a more complex phenomenon. It may be that online disinhibition is a

situation - specific behaviour rather than a stable psychological process for this group of participants.

The results must be considered in light of the exploratory nature of the study and the small sample size. Additionally, the use of self-report measures may have impacted the results due to social desirability biases. Future studies utilizing larger and more varied samples, as well as mixed-methods designs, may offer more information on the relationship between digital behaviors and mental health for young adults.

Conclusion

The current study sought to investigate the relationship between mental health, online disinhibition, and online identity and self-presentation among college students aged 18-25 years. The study employed a correlational research design to collect data using self-report instruments administered via Google Forms.

The results showed a significant positive correlation between mental health and online identity and self-presentation, and no significant correlations between mental health and online disinhibition or online disinhibition and online identity and self-presentation. The results of the study indicate that positive mental health may be associated with healthy and authentic online self-presentation practices among young adults.

Although the current study had a small sample size and relied on self-report instruments, the study offers initial evidence for the relationship between online behavior and mental health. Future studies may consider using larger and more representative samples, longitudinal designs, and more rigorous statistical analyses to investigate these relationships. Moreover, using qualitative research methods such as interviews may provide a richer understanding of the online experiences of college students.

The results of the study emphasize the need for promoting responsible online behavior and mental health awareness among college students in today's technology-saturated context.

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